

Updating the Great Britain Historical GIS, and the Vision of Britain web site

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Summary

Visualising census data is complicated by changes over time in both reporting geographies and variables collected. The website, A Vision of Britain Through Time, was designed as a gateway for the general public to easily learn about their area's past. Having run for over twenty years the website continues to provide this basic information, but the team are investing time and effort into innovative new ways to communicate the rich data held in the site. New research council funding is allowing the development of a prototype AI interface alongside improvements to the usability and content of the existing site.

KEYWORDS: Census, Statistics, Artificial Intelligence, Data visualisation, Time series

1. Introduction

The Great Britain Historical GIS, now based at the University of Portsmouth, is an old resource, dating back more than thirty years, and its public web site, A Vision of Britain through Time (<http://www.VisionOfBritain.org.uk>) has been online for over twenty years. It has weathered many server migrations, and transitions both from ArcGIS to open source tools and from Ingres database software to Oracle and then to PostgreSQL; and content has steadily expanded (Gregory and Southall, 1998; Southall, 2011, 2012 and 2014).

However, the pandemic period and the general aging of the web site's software has led to an accumulation of problems and a decline in usage. We report here on work since 2023 to renew the resource and, in particular, to improve both the discoverability and the visualisation of the statistical content. This work is funded through two substantial Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) projects, plus commercial earnings mainly from licensing historical digital boundary data. We are near the end of the Data Discovery Made Easy (DDME) project, funded as part of the ESRC's Future Data Services programme, while just starting the "Democracy and Social Change" project, so this is mainly a presentation of the DDME research, the resulting enhancements to the web site, and the prototype AI-driven natural language search interface.

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2. Background

Vision of Britain was originally funded by the National Lottery, and consequently was designed to serve a much wider audience than most online geospatial systems created by university-based projects, or the download systems operated by the UK Data Service. We feel that recent Data Service developments have over-prioritised the needs of data scientists, with the programming skills needed to work with data APIs, and have consequently neglected the needs not just of the general public but of most social science academics. One part of the DDME project is therefore a survey of user needs based on in-depth interviews with researchers in human geography, sociology, social policy and economics. The focus is on their experience with different online data services, and more generally on how they find the data they need.

We have ourselves been getting extensive recent experience with those online services, as another part of the project is updating our statistical content not just to include 2021 census data (2022 for Scotland), but adding ward-level data for greater geographical detail. Vision of Britain is very unusual among online census data systems in emphasising census time series as much as mapping, but here it has to overcome constant changes in census geography through GIS-based redistricting. Given our very extensive reconstructions of past reporting geographies, vector overlay methods can transform statistical datasets from one geography to another, but the results are problematic unless the input geography is at least as detailed as the output.

3. Updating Vision of Britain

Up to now, this has limited our long-run time series to local government districts, but on the one hand mergers to create unitary authorities are making Britain's local government geography ever cruder, and on the other there is now a long enough run of census small area statistics, for Output Areas or Enumeration Districts, to construct useful time series. We are therefore redistricting data from at least the last five censuses to construct consistent time series for three output geographies: current local government districts, the c. 8,000 current local government wards and, to support the "Democracy and Social Change" project, the new constituency geography introduced for the 2024 General Election. However, this work is complicated by differences between the outputs provided by the three UK census offices, and by growing problems accessing "historical censuses" even as recent as 1991.

Figure 1 Asians as percent of total population in 1991, mapped for 2024 Wards

Making the resulting data accessible not as downloads but in both maps and time series graphs requires an unusual data structure, in which all data values are held in a single column of a single table, with many millions of rows, and each with their own metadata which includes

location, date, meaning and source. “Location” is recorded via an ID number drawn from a large poly-hierarchic ontology of administrative/reporting units, which connects to a single table of dated boundary polygons (Southall and Aucott, 2019). “Meaning” is expressed in another ontology which groups data values into hypercubes and assigns these to broader themes. This Data Documentation System (DDS) very directly drives graphical visualisations (Southall, 2008). Work for DDME includes updating and extending an editor for the administrative unit ontology (AUO) and creating a new editor for the DDS, making it accessible to team members who are not intimately familiar with the somewhat abstract data model.

4. Prototyping a machine learning-based natural language interface

A central element of the DDME project is developing a prototype natural language interface, driven by a large language model (LLM), and here the GBHGIS team are collaborating with a research software engineering team based in the University of Portsmouth’s Institute of Cosmology and Gravitation. The aim here is very much to further develop Vision of Britain as a statistical resource “for the rest of us”, reducing the need for users to be familiar either with past reporting geographies or specialised statistical terminology. For example, people looking for statistics on education, specifically “Qualifications”, can use natural language to filter the data to ask “Please show me the data on Qualifications in Surrey between the years of 1950 and 2020”. There is precedent for this kind of system, with Microsoft introducing a natural language functionality into Power BI (their popular data visualisation program) for users to be able to “ask their data questions” as early as 2015 (Microsoft, 2015).

In Figure 2 we present the high level software diagram for the natural language interface, with the blue block on the right representing the overview of the user interface, the green block in the middle representing the workflow and control of the user interaction, and the orange block on the left showing the language model components.

While the original plan was to rely on ChatGPT, the resulting access fees would have made it hard to include the new interface within a completely open access resource. We are now working with the DeepSeek-R1 (32B) LLM running locally on a PC-based server with a powerful graphics processing unit (GPU), and are able to swap between alternative models easily, taking advantage of the rapid pace of LLM development. This ability to use local LLMs means we can look towards a future public service if and when new capital funding enables replacement of the current Vision of Britain servers, which run PostgreSQL well but completely lack GPUs.

The use of LLMs in this application must be handled with great care to prevent erroneous responses, hallucinations, and providing data analysis. It is for this reason that the application is programmed to give as little freedom as possible to the LLM with results being drawn from the data residing in the database at every opportunity. This means the LLM will be restricted to specific functionality that we have defined and retain control over.

As well as the prototype new interface, the final part of our work is to enhance the current Vision of Britain interface to better access the very extensive statistical content. The current interface arguably works very well indeed as a gazetteer of Britain, including many historical place names as well as current names, but the very accessible “places” layer (Southall, 2014) tends to hide the more formal information on units and statistics.

Figure 2 Natural Language Interface: High Level Software Diagram

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Biographies

Humphrey Southall is a Professor of Historical Geography and the principal creator of the Great Britain Historical GIS. His research interests include the origins of Britain's north-south divide and data models for rich gazetteers.

Xan Morice-Atkinson is a Research Software Engineer and an expert in machine learning. He previously worked at National Air Traffic Services, where he designed, developed, and maintained aspects of their data processing and analysis pipeline as they migrated to a new platform.

Paula Aucott is a Senior Research Associate specialising in historical GIS. She has masters degrees in English local history and GIS, and has been part of the Great Britain Historical GIS team for over twenty years. She is project managing our current ESRC-funded projects.

John Westwood is a Research Associate and geospatial programmer who worked on the GBHGIS in 2002-4, and 2007-14, when he was principally responsible for the creation of the Vision of Britain map library. He currently has principal responsibility for the new metadata editors.